

16th CIRIAF National Congress

Sustainable Development, Human Health and Environmental Protection

Net Zero Energy settlements in Europe: first findings of the Zero-Plus Horizon 2020 project

Anna Laura Pisello ^{1,2,*}, Cristina Piselli ¹, Gloria Pignatta ¹, Claudia Fabiani ¹, Filippo Ubertini ³, Franco Cotana ^{1,2}, and Mat Santamouris ⁴

¹ CIRIAF-Interuniversity Research Center, University of Perugia, Via G. Duranti 67, Perugia, Italy

² Department of Engineering, University of Perugia, Via G. Duranti 93, Perugia, Italy

³ Department of Civil and Environmental Engineering, University of Perugia, Perugia, Italy

⁴ National and Kapodistrian University of Athens, 30 Panepistimiou Ave, Athens, Greece

* Author to whom correspondence should be addressed. E-Mail: anna.pisello@unipg.it

Abstract: Energy efficiency in buildings up to near zero energy buildings is a key research issue recently under investigation. Net Zero Energy (NZE) settlements aim at optimizing energy performance and indoor-outdoor microclimate at larger scale, i.e. neighborhood dimension. In this view, the University of Perugia (CIRIAF group) is working on an International Horizon 2020 successful project entitled “ZERO-PLUS project: Achieving near Zero and Positive Energy Settlements in Europe using Advanced Energy Technology”, that started on October 2015. In this project, a comprehensive, cost-effective system for NZE settlements is developed and implemented in four case studies: in Italy, Cyprus, UK, and France. In these case studies, a multifunctional integration of active technologies and passive systems is designed, optimized, and monitored, in order to achieve less than 20 kWh/m²y of energy need and more than 50 kWh/m²y of renewable energy production, with at least 16% lower cost than the current ones. In this panorama, the UNIPG group is responsible of bridging the gap between building scale and neighborhood scale, and of the design, optimization, and analysis of the Italian case study settlement, among others. Therefore, this work presents the project general framework and the first achievements carried out by the authors together with the other partners. In particular, results of first thermal-energy performance analysis of the Italian case study buildings, performed through dynamic simulation, are shown. Findings demonstrate how an aware building design coupled with innovative energy systems produce key improvements in building thermal-energy performance up to energy need lower than 10 kWh/m²y.

Keywords: Net Zero Energy Buildings; Net Zero Energy settlements; ZERO-PLUS project; Horizon 2020; Renewable energy technologies; Thermal-energy dynamic simulation; Solar energy; Energy efficiency in buildings.

1. Introduction and research background

The dynamic construction sector has a large potential to improve the quality of human life and transforming society. Nowadays, however buildings significantly affect the global and local climate and environment by consuming resources and energy and producing pollution and waste [1]. In fact, the buildings are responsible of a wide amount of the global final energy consumption and carbon emissions [2,3]. In Europe, over 40% of the final energy use and 36% of greenhouse gas emissions are due to the building sector [4]. Therefore, the mitigation of the energy and environmental impact of building stock is a key issue addressed by energy policies through the enhancement of building energy efficiency and renewable energy technologies [5,6].

In this view, the Net Zero Energy Building (Net ZEB) is a newly developed building concept within the international scientific and governmental community [7]. Indeed, the recast of the Energy Performance of Buildings Directive (EPBD) 2010/31/EU states that all new buildings should be “nearly zero energy” by 2020, while all new public buildings by 2018 [8]. The Net ZEB concept is based on the basically zero external energy need, i.e. buildings requiring small amount of energy and, therefore, contributing minimally to the emission of greenhouse gases [9]. The reduced energy consumption and the microclimate improvement [10,11] results from (i) passive design strategies enhancing building energy efficiency and (ii) renewable energy and low-carbon sources covering the most of the remaining building loads [12]. Since the early 2000s the interest on Net ZEB has been growing and several case studies have been built and deeply studied [5, 13-21]. In this panorama, Kapsalaki et al. [3] developed a methodology, including a calculation platform, aimed at assisting the choice of the economic efficient design solutions for residential NZEB, by taking into account local climate, available energy resources, and economic conditions. Fanney et al. [2] studied the performance of a Net-Zero Energy Residential Test Facility built in Maryland, USA in order to achieve net-zero for a house with conventional architecture, amenities, and size, by including renewable energy and energy efficient technologies.

In recent years, researches expanded the zero energy concept to a wider scale, i.e. the Net Zero Energy Community. The Net Zero Energy Community concept is more complex than the Net ZEB because energy use in a community as an integrated system involving different energy end-use sectors [22]. In a NZE community the reduced energy needs are reached through efficiency gains owing to the balance of energy for vehicles, thermal, and electrical energy within the community, which is met by renewable energy, and the integrated management of community needs through smart grid. The Net Zero Energy Community system is still under development and few researches on this topic [4,23] and real case studies have been developed. An existing NZE settlement is the Beddington Zero Energy Development (BedZED) in London, UK, completed in 2002 [24]. It is composed by eight mixed-used residential and office buildings built considering both renewable energy production, embodied energy of buildings, and bioclimatic architecture principles. Monitoring demonstrated an average electricity demand of buildings on average 80% lower than a conventional local building. Another example is the “Solar settlement” in Schlierberg, Germany, completed in 2006 [25]. The settlement design followed the classic solar house design concepts in order to maximize active and passive utilization of solar energy, since it is located in a heating-dominated climate. In

terms of its primary energy balance, it generates twice as much energy as it consumes, i.e. it is a “plus energy” community.

The improvement of building stock effectiveness is also a key issue considered in the EU H2020 programme, i.e. the EU financial instrument for Research and Innovation aimed at securing Europe's global competitiveness [26]. In fact, the construction sector has a relevant influence in the global economy [1,27]. In particular, the H2020 “Climate Action, Environment, Resource Efficiency and Raw Materials” section focuses on the achievement of a resource efficient and climate change resilient economy and society by keeping average global warming below 2°C, which is largely affected by the built environment.

In this panorama, the International Horizon 2020 ZERO-PLUS project is aimed at sprawling the boundaries from Net ZEB to NZE settlements. In this project, a comprehensive and cost-effective modular system for NZE residential neighborhoods will be developed, including the definition of guidelines for its design, construction, monitoring, and assessment. Such system will be implemented in four demonstration case study settlements throughout Europe, with varying climate and building typologies. The final purpose is to ensure a rapid market uptake of this system that will significantly reduce NZE settlements costs.

The present contribution introduces the main aims and Work Packages (WPs) of the ZERO-PLUS project by focusing the attention to the role of authors' work. The four case study settlements, i.e. Italian, Cypriot, English, and French, and the innovative renewable energy technologies and efficient systems involved in the project are briefly described. Finally, the paper widely discuss on the performance calculation at the design stage of the Italian case study buildings. The main results of the thermal-energy performance analysis, carried out via dynamic simulation, are presented and discussed.

2. The ZERO-PLUS project

The “ZERO-PLUS: Achieving near Zero and Positive Energy Settlements in Europe using Advanced Energy Technology” is an International Horizon 2020 EU project successfully proposed by a consortium of academic and commercial partners, including the University of Perugia. The partnership is coordinated by the University of Athens, Greece, led by Prof. Mat Santamouris, and involves sixteen partners from different countries, i.e. Greece, Italy, Cyprus, France, UK, Germany, Switzerland, and Israel.

The purpose of the ZERO-PLUS project is to develop and implement in four case study settlements in Europe, i.e. in Italy, Cyprus, France, and UK, a comprehensive and cost-effective system for Net Zero Energy settlements. The system is composed of innovative solutions for the building envelope, for building energy generation and management, and for energy management at the settlement level. Technologies will be integrated in a system optimally designed and implemented in each demonstration case study settlement according to the different local climate and building types. The results of their implementation will be monitored, analyzed, and disseminated and a comprehensive market analysis and business plan will support the commercial exploitation of the results. The project aims at ensuring a rapid market uptake of the developed innovative system for NZE residential settlements, in order to reduce their cost.

To this aim, the project has the following Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) and goals:

- Reduce the operational energy usage in residential buildings to an average of 0-20 kWh/m² per year.
- Generate at least 50 kWh/m² renewable energy per year, on average, in the NZE settlement.
- Reduce the cost of NZE settlements by at least 16%, compared with current costs.
- Support the shift towards resource-efficient, low-carbon and climate-resilient buildings and districts, by reducing carbon footprint by almost 77 kg_{CO2}/m² with a total 408 tons CO₂ offset for all ZERO-PLUS case studies.

KPIs will be achieved through the transition from single NZE buildings to NZE settlements, in which the energy loads and resources are optimally managed and innovative energy production technologies integrated. Accordingly, solutions for the distribution network, energy storage and micro grid control on a district level, as well as an optimum climatic management of the open spaces in the settlement will be implemented. Furthermore, an approach of mass customization will be employed in order to reduce balance of system costs.

Therefore, the ZERO-PLUS project is divided in ten WPs spread along four years, from October 2015 until September 2019. WPs are listed as follows:

- WP1: State of the art on NZE and Positive Energy Settlements: Initial Preparation and Collection of Data in the Four Demonstration Sites;
- WP2: Design and Optimization of Modular Envelope Components;
- WP3: Energy Production and Management of Individual Buildings;
- WP4: Integrated Design and Optimization of the NZE Technologies to be implemented at the Settlements Level – Creation of Simulation and Monitoring Protocols (led by UNIPG);
- WP5: Integrated Design and Optimization of the Zero Energy Settlements;
- WP6: Construction Management, Cost Management and Implementation of the Innovative Technologies;
- WP7: Monitoring and Evaluation of the Settlements' Performance;
- WP8: Market Analysis and Model for Business Growth;
- WP9: Dissemination;
- WP10: Consortium Management.

3. Case studies and innovative energy technologies

In this section, the four case study settlements involved in the ZERO-PLUS project, i.e. in Peyia, Paphos, Cyprus; in Novafeltria, Rimini, Italy; in Voreppe, Grenoble, France; and in Derwenthorpe, York, UK, are presented and briefly described. The four case studies have been selected in order to represent different climate contexts and building typologies.

Furthermore, the main technical characteristics of the innovative renewable energy technologies and energy efficient systems implemented in the project are reported.

3.1. Case studies

3.1.1. Peyia Village, Paphos, Cyprus

The Cypriot case study settlement is located in the outskirts of Peyia village, Paphos, in the South-West region of Cyprus. The total construction settlement is divided in (i) an area for a rehabilitation center of about 25000 m² and (ii) a residential area composed by 123 autonomous plots of about 850 m² each and 9-apartment buildings with a total area of 11000 m². The areas involved in the ZERO-PLUS project are two autonomous plots (total surface of about 2.000 m²) with individual residential luxury villas (Figure 1a). There are two villa types, Type 1 (building surface about 270 m²) and Type 2 (building surface about 160 m²).

The settlement is located at about 430 m a.s.l. in a hillside area, adjacent to a luxuriant forest and green area. The climate is mild Mediterranean, generally warm and temperate, with a average annual temperature of 18.3°C (Köppen-Geiger climate classification Csa) [28]. Annual global solar radiation on horizontal surface is equal to 1900-2100 kWh/m².

3.1.2. Novafeltria, Rimini, Italy

The Italian case study settlement is located Loc. Secchiano Marecchia, Novafeltria, Rimini, in the South of Emilia-Romagna region in the center-East of Italy. The settlement is integrated in a growing residential expansion area which is very close to a public green area. The total construction settlement includes ten residential single-family buildings and six apartment buildings (total surface of about 30000 m²). The ZERO-PLUS project will involve four single-family terraced villas with private garden (Figure 1b), each one in a square ground lot of about 400 m² (total surface 2500 m²). Two similar villa types (Figure 2), Typology A and Typology B (each one characterized by a total floor area of about 130 m²) are designed. The villas are designed to host one family of about three to five people.

The settlement is located at about 215 m a.s.l. in flat area of Po Valley, close to the first hills of the Apennines. The climate is Temperate and Mediterranean, with 2294 degree days (Köppen-Geiger climate classification Cfa) [28]. Annual global solar radiation on horizontal surface is equal to 1429 kWh/m².

3.1.3. Voreppe, Grenoble, France

The French case study settlement is located in Voreppe, Grenoble, in the Auvergne-Rhône-Alpes region in the South-East of France. The total construction settlement includes a 28-dwellings building for social selling (vertically oriented building in Figure 1c) and the ZERO-PLUS case study building consisting of a 20-collective dwellings building (horizontally oriented building in Figure 1c) for social renting (around 1400 m² inhabited area). The total settlement area is about 3000 m². Dwellings will be on the ground floor plus three floors above, distributed around a central column. A shared underground parking lot will be created for both buildings.

The settlement is located at about 203 m a.s.l. in plain area surrounded by mountains: Chartreuse on the East and Vercors on the West. The climate is half-oceanic and half-continental with a design

external temperature equal to -11°C (Köppen-Geiger climate classification Cfb) [28]. Annual global solar radiation on horizontal surface is equal to 1366 kWh/m^2 .

3.1.4. Derwenthorpe Community, York, UK

The British case study settlement is located in Derwenthorpe, a village in the East outskirts of York, in the North Yorkshire region of UK. The total settlement design has been developed in four phases and 18 of the 54 acres (218.500 m^2) will be open land available for public open space. The settlement provides an overall intervention of 500 homes including 2, 3, 4, and 5-bedroom housings with private garden and other 1-bedroom apartments. The buildings involved in the ZERO-PLUS project are three detached single-family dwellings of two different types (N1 and N3) with three bedrooms, split over two floors (floor surface 95 m^2) (Figure 1d). Each dwelling can host an average of three people, with a maximum of five people.

The settlement is located at about 16 m a.s.l. in flat area of fertile arable land bordered by the Pennines. The climate is warm Temperate, with fully humid, warm summer and 2303 degree days (Köppen-Geiger climate classification Cfb) [28]. Annual global solar radiation on horizontal surface is equal to 1294 kWh/m^2 .

Figure 1. Plan of the four case study settlements: (a) Cyprus, (b) Italy, (c) France, (d) UK.

Figure 2. Render of the Italian case study building.

3.2. Innovative energy technologies

3.2.1. Advanced envelope components by FIBRAN

The advanced envelope components by FIBRAN [29] involves three different materials:

- XPS extruded polystyrene (designation code XPS (Extruded Polystyrene) EN 13164 – CS(10\Y)300-DS(70,90)-TR400-WL(T)1,5);
- Cool Plaster for facades;
- Cool ceramic Tiles for flat roof.

These three components can be installed separately or integrated, i.e. XPS+Cool Plaster for external walls or XPS+Cool Tiles for flat roofs (Figure 3a). Therefore, it is a composite cool and thermal insulating material, based on a new generation of extruded polystyrene. The two alternative final coatings, i.e. Cool Tile and Cool Plaster, are characterized by high solar reflectance and high thermal emittance (Table 1). Moreover, they have been optimized to have extra self-cleaning capability through photocatalytic properties. The system is suitable for various climatic regions and for new and existing buildings, and present an easy and low-cost construction method.

Table 1. FIBRAN advanced envelope components thermal and optical characteristics.

	Thermal conductivity [W/m K]	Density [kg/m ³]	Specific heat capacity [J/kg K]	Thermal emittance [-]	Solar Reflectance [-]	Visible Reflectance [-]
XPS	0.034	32	1500	-	-	-
Cool Plaster	0.087	1800	1100	0.83	0.71	0.77
Cool Tile	1.300	2500	840	0.85	0.58	0.51

3.2.2. FREESCOO air conditioning system by SOLARINVENT

FREESCOO (FREE Solar COoling) is a compact solar air conditioning system designed for ventilation, cooling, dehumidification, and heating of buildings [30]. The unit is based on a new solar Desiccant Evaporative Cooling (DEC) concept. In fact, solar heat and water are used to drive the cooling process for conditioning the space connected with the unit. The system guarantees the temperature and humidity control, and the air change in the conditioned space. In the wintertime, the system can act as a heat distribution system when connected to a solar concentrating production system. *FREESCOO* can be configured to be installed over building roof (Figure 3b), both on flat and sloped roofs, or integrated in the building wall. Solar PV panels can be integrated to fulfil the required electricity. The system is characterized by a cooling power of 2.7 KW in 2 m² with 150W of maximum power absorption. Also, it has a EER for cooling equal to 13.

3.2.3. Building Integrated PV by SBskin

Building Integrated PV (BIPV) by SBskin [31] are precast, dry-assembled, and pre-stressed translucent building integrated glass blocks, which are integrated with Dye Sensitized Solar Cells (DSC) photovoltaics components. They can be installed in translucent building façades and roofs.

Such system performs as an active and passive system simultaneously, due to a transparency up to 50%. The electricity production is equal to 1 kWp in 15-20 m². There are three possible configurations:

- *ThermoGB*: glass blocks with a thermal belt in recycled plastic material to which the two glass shells composing the glass block are glued. The thermal belt houses a sheet of transparent insulating material (aerogel, glass, low-e or polycarbonate).
- *SolarGB*: glass blocks integrating colorful (in various colors) and translucent DSC and thus functioning as PV building element.
- *ThermoSolarGB*: glass blocks integrating the two above mentioned system and thus providing PV energy production and high thermal insulation.

In the ZERO-PLUS project the third typology is considered (Figure 3c).

3.2.4. BEMS and Home Automation by ABB

Home Automation Systems coupled using Mesh Asynchronous Dynamic Wireless Sensors Networks are considered with incorporated wireless communication. The mesh network consists of (i) a self-forming multi-hop mesh of nodes, which collect and relay data from sensors and actuators, and (ii) a network coordinator that monitors and manages network performance and security, and exchanges data with a host application. Also, it is asynchronous, i.e. each device can transmit its data to another one at any time, without depending on time scheduling, and dynamic, i.e. the addition of new devices (routers and/or sensors) is enabled without meaningful efforts in terms of configuration or energy consumption. The system is used for the management of occupants' indoor comfort and actions. Furthermore, interconnection with integrated resources management system at settlement level (sub-section 3.2.8) is achievable. Based on existing applications, the system is able to provide 20-30 % of annual energy consumption reduction.

Figure 3. ZERO-PLUS innovative energy efficient and renewable energy production technologies: (a) FIBRAN XPS+Cool Tile, (b) FREESCOO, (c) BIPV.

3.2.5. *WindRail* solar and wind driven energy system by ANERDGY

The *WindRail* technology uses in an efficient and economical way the natural resources in order to provide all season energy [32]. In fact, it is a modular wind turbine system that harnesses the energy of the wind, by exploiting the pressure differences around the building (usually in the façade/roof

corner), and the solar radiation to generate electricity. Solar photovoltaic cells or partial/full solar thermal panels can be integrated to contribute to electricity or thermal energy generation, respectively. The system can be building integrated or installed off-shore as stand-alone. In order to serve different building needs, two different types of this system are available, both focused on a hybrid solution to utilize wind and sun in one system: C-Type (Figure 4a), for larger flat installations over large flat or sloped roof buildings or inclined wind exposed ground surfaces; and B-Type, for small domestic buildings sloped roofs or ground off-shore installations. The *WindRail* has a generation time/year ratio of about 45-95% and an energy yield of 200-650 kWh/m², depending on the type and installation site.

3.2.6. *FRESCO* Solar Linear Fresnel Collector + TES tank by ARCA

FRESCO is a photovoltaic/solar thermal (PV/ST) compact Linear Fresnel Collector (LFC) for polygenerative applications (Figure 4b). The Linear Fresnel solar Collector is able to concentrate the solar radiation onto a receiver tube in order to generate thermal energy. In small units, flat PV panels can be coupled on the reverse side of the mirrors. In this way, when the direct solar irradiation is low mirrors are reverse and diffuse solar radiation is used to produce electricity by PV panels. The produced thermal energy is collected at about 250°C and is stored inside a Thermal Energy Storage (TES) tank. The storage tank can (i) directly heat buildings or (ii) can also serve chillers for thermal energy transformation into cooling energy. The LFC can be building integrated over a flat roof or installed off-shore on land, canopies of parking lots or industrial roofing in the settlement area. Anyhow, the system has to be installed in free field conditions in horizontal position and oriented in North-South direction. Furthermore, a minimum number of modules for installation (7-8 modules for a total length of 28-32 m) are required in order to reduce the “end-effect”, i.e. when the direct solar irradiation is reflected outside the collection pipe due to high beam inclination, that limits drastically the overall efficiency of the system. An energy production of 11 kW_{th} peak at 850 W/m² DNI per module (4x8x4(h)) m, 22 m² of net mirror surface) can be achieved.

3.2.7. *FAE* High Concentrating PV by ARCA

High Concentrating Photovoltaic (HCPV) systems exploit the property of optics (lenses or curved mirrors) to focus the sun radiation impacting a wide area on a small area occupied by one or more high efficiency photovoltaic cells (up to 44% of conversion rate) in order to generate electricity. The *FAE* HCPV module (Figure 4c) is designed with integrated active cooling system for combined heat and electricity generation. ARCA has proposed to use the *FAE* HCPV technology instead of the *FRESCO* Solar LFC and TES tank in certain case studies due to *FRESCO* system installation problems in such contexts. If compared with classic PV modules, HCPV systems are characterized by a sensible reduction of the active element size. The HCPV efficiency is about 75% with an electrical efficiency of about 30%. The temperature of the HTF can be raised up to 70°C. The system has a Alt-Alt type tracker that has to be installed in a flat area and in free field conditions, in order to get the maximum possible solar radiation, with the primary axis mounted in North-South direction.

3.2.8. Integrated Energy Resources Management systems by ABB

The Integrated Energy Resources Management by ABB [33] is a dynamically interactive real-time infrastructure that incorporates an innovative technology that allows the two-way communication between the energy utility and its customers/users. Integrated Resource Management can be coupled with Smart Grids for applications with far-reaching inter-disciplinary impacts: (i) providing the capacity to safely integrate more renewable energy sources, smart buildings and distributed generators into the network, (ii) delivering power more efficiently and reliably through demand response and comprehensive control and monitoring capabilities, (iii) using automatic grid reconfiguration to prevent or restore outages (self-healing capabilities), and (iv) enabling consumers to have greater control over their electricity consumption and to actively participate in the electricity market. Possible 10% cost reduction can be achieved by minimization of cabling and 50% energy costs reduction by optimization procedures.

The Integrated Energy Resources Management system is composed of different integrated technologies:

- PV with integrated solar inverter and storage system, for building installations.
- Medium Voltage (MV) distribution network: it collects the renewable energy produced and distributes it to the loads within the settlement.
- Low Voltage (LV) distribution network: provides the necessary connectivity between the energy production and the energy demand in low voltage.
- Micro grid power management: Smart Grid with power flows management functions in the settlement and balance of the access to renewables, storage, and other sources via Wi-Fi network.
- *EcoDry* high efficiency distribution transformers: used to connect low voltage energy sources and loads to the medium voltage network.
- *Public Lighting Management (PLM)* i-illumination system: is an efficiency optimization solution to control and power public lighting.

Figure 4. ZERO-PLUS innovative renewable energy production technologies: (a) *WindRail*, (b) *FRESCO* LFC, (c) *FAE* HCPV.

4. Dynamic thermal-energy analysis of the Italian case study buildings

Dynamic simulations have been performed in order to (i) carry out a preliminary design of the Italian case study settlement buildings and of the innovative technologies to be effectively implemented in the buildings, and to (ii) assess the thermal-energy performance of the ZERO-PLUS buildings with respect to traditional and innovative reference buildings. In this work, the sole building integrated energy efficient systems and technologies for renewable energy production have been considered, while technologies to be implemented at settlement level and energy management technologies will be discussed in future steps of the project.

4.1. Buildings simulation

The thermal-energy dynamic simulation has been carried out in free-running and thermostatically-controlled conditions by means of *EnergyPlus* simulation engine [34] with *DesignBuilder* graphical interface. Although the Italian case study settlement involves the design of four buildings, only two villas (87 m² of conditioned area each) are analyzed in this work. In fact, the four villas are all detached dwellings characterized by similar geometry, materials, and orientation. Villas are placed in two parallel lines in the settlement, two in each line, at a distance of about 20 m along the line and 16 m from one line to another (Figure 1b). The sole difference between the villas in the two lines is that their plan distribution is overturned, but the pitched roof orientation is the same for all the four villas. Therefore, the four project villas show very similar thermal-energy behavior and a variation of about 3% can be considered when evaluating the remaining two buildings. The two analyzed villas, characterized by overturned plant orientation, are reported as Typology A and Typology B.

Furthermore, a thermal comfort analysis has been carried out through the “Thermal comfort calculator” tool of *DesignBuilder* by considering the data of year round simulation under thermostatically-controlled conditions of the ten building scenarios, five for Typology A and five for Typology B. The “Thermal comfort calculator” tool is based on indications of Fanger model and enables to calculate PMV (Predicted Mean Vote) and PPD (Percentage of Person Dissatisfied) indexes. The comfort range is defined according to EN ISO 7730: 2005 [37] indications.

Seasonal comfort indexes have been calculated for the ten buildings scenarios, i.e. for winter, spring, summer, and autumn. The tool requires as input data the seasonal average indoor Air Temperature, Mean Radiant Temperature, Relative Humidity, and Air Speed, which have been set according to the simulation results. Furthermore, the met, i.e. the metabolic rate, has been set to a standard 1.2 value, while the clo unit, i.e. clothing insulation, has been provided depending on the analyzed season, as follows:

- clo = 1.25 in winter;
- clo = 1 in autumn and spring;
- clo = 0.75 in summer.

Therefore, seasonal PMV, PPD, and average indoor Operative Temperature values are given as output by the tool.

4.2. Buildings scenarios

In order to assess the thermal-energy performance of the ZERO-PLUS project Italian buildings with respect to realistic traditional and innovative reference Italian buildings, five buildings scenarios have been defined:

- i. Reference_typical: reference buildings according to Italian typical construction typology;
- ii. Reference_regulation: reference buildings according to Italian current building regulation;
- iii. Baseline: design buildings according to the proposed ZERO-PLUS project;
- iv. Baseline+: Baseline buildings with implemented established energy-efficient (EE) technologies or settings aimed at minimizing demand for electricity, space heating, and cooling;
- v. Zero Plus_reduction+generation: Baseline+ where the selected reduction and generation ZERO-PLUS technologies at building level are implemented according to the project-specific energy conservation and energy generation solutions.

The five scenarios of the two case study buildings present the same characteristics in terms of:

- building geometry and dimensions;
- building orientation and surroundings;
- occupancy and appliances schedules, according to *DesignBuilder* standard “Residential spaces” template (UK standard).

For all the five scenarios, the set-point temperatures are set at 20°C and 26°C for heating and cooling, respectively. Further building models information, i.e. envelope, lighting, and plants characteristics, have been defined according to the different building scenarios and are reported in the following sub-sections.

4.2.1. Reference_typical buildings

The first reference buildings, Reference_typical, have been modeled according to the “Building Typology Brochure for Italy” of IEE Project TABULA (Typology Approach for BUilDing stock energy Assessment, 2009-2012) [35] and by considering the statistical national data available for the Italian territory showing that the large majority of the existing Italian building stock was built between 1945 and 1981. In fact, the above-mentioned project was aimed at developing residential building typologies for 13 European countries. Each national typology consists of a classification scheme grouping buildings according to their size, age, and further parameters and a set of exemplary buildings representing the building types.

The characteristics of the main envelope components are reported in Table 2. For the lighting system, the “Tungsten lamp” template of *DesignBuilder* has been selected, characterized by an associated energy of 20 W/m²-100 lux. The HVAC system consists of gas boiler for both heating and DHW with efficiency equal to 0.8. Nor cooling system, neither mechanical ventilation are installed. Air infiltration has been set to 1 ac/h (air changes/hour).

4.2.2. Reference_regulation buildings

The Reference_regulation buildings, instead, have been modeled according to the current Italian regulation for new buildings construction, i.e. DM 26/06/2015 – Application of methods for energy performance calculation and definition of requirements and minimum standards of buildings [36], that was developed according to the European Directive 2010/31/UE [8]. Such regulation gives indications on both the minimum requirements of new constructions and the reference building calculation.

The characteristics of the main envelope components are reported in Table 2. Low-e double glazing with Argon gap has been considered by selecting the “Dbl LoE (e2=.1) Clr 3mm/13mm Arg” template of *DesignBuilder*. For the lighting system, the reference “Italy” template of *DesignBuilder* has been selected, characterized by an associated energy of 3.4 W/m²-100 lux. The HVAC system consists of an air-to-water heat pump with COP equal to 3.0 for heating and 2.5 for DHW and cooling, according to indications in [36]. The mechanical ventilation system is the same as the Baseline building, i.e. air supply of approximately 300 m³/h for the whole building excluding the circulation area and the unconditioned zones. Air infiltration has been set to 0.5 ac/h.

4.2.3. Baseline buildings

The Baseline buildings have been modeled according to the preliminary ZERO-PLUS project buildings indications.

The characteristics of the main envelope components are reported in Table 2. All the two roof typologies, the external walls, and the windows blinds present an external cool coating. Low-e double glazing with Argon gap has been considered by selecting the “Dbl LoE (e2=.1) Clr 3mm/13mm Arg” template of *DesignBuilder*, as for the Reference_regulation buildings. For the lighting system, the “LED” template of *DesignBuilder* has been selected, characterized by an associated energy of 3.3 W/m²-100 lux. Also, the lighting control has been considered. The HVAC system consists of an air-to-water heat pump with COP equal to 4.1 and EER equal to 3.8, according to the project design. The mechanical ventilation supplies approximately 300 m³/h for the whole buildings excluding the circulation area and the unconditioned zones. Air infiltration has been set to 0.3 ac/h.

4.2.4. Baseline+ buildings

The Baseline+ buildings have been modeled according to the ZERO-PLUS preliminary project building indications by applying the established EE technologies or settings to the Baseline model to minimize demand for electricity, space heating and cooling.

The Baseline model is already modeled considering high energy-efficiency solutions, i.e. lighting, HVAC systems, transparent envelope components, envelope materials and insulation, cool skin, energy production system. Therefore, the only established EE settings and technologies implemented in the model are:

- for the natural ventilation, the “minimum fresh air per person”;
- for the mechanical ventilation, the air-to-air heat exchanger (heat recovery) with 70% of efficiency;

- PV + storage by ABB. At the moment, for energy generation we considered 18 PV panels (for a total area of about 30 m²) characterized by:
 - Total power: 4.5 kW
 - Fraction of surface with active solar cells: 90%
 - Cell efficiency value: 0.15

4.2.5. Zero Plus_reduction+generation buildings

The Zero Plus_reduction+generation buildings has been modeled by adding the selected ZERO-PLUS technologies for the Italian case study buildings to the Baseline+ model (according to the project description in the Grant Agreement).

The ZERO-PLUS building integrated technologies implemented in the Italian buildings models are summarized as follows:

- XPS by FIBRAN;
- Cool Plaster for facades by FIBRAN (2 mm thickness);
- Cool Tiles for flat roof by FIBRAN (8 mm thickness);
- *FREESCOO* (HVAC) system by SOLARINVENT:
 - EER = 13 (as declared by the technology producer as partner of the project (SOLARINVENT), the EER value is exactly the electric efficiency of the system in the summer period, i.e. the electric COP).
 - Modeled as cooling system.

Table 2. Different envelope characteristics in the two Reference and the Baseline buildings scenarios.

Envelope component	Reference_typical		Reference_regulation		Baseline & Baseline+		Zero Plus_r+g	
	"U" value [W/m ² K]	R _{solar} [%]	"U" value [W/m ² K]	R _{solar} [%]	"U" value [W/m ² K]	R _{solar} [%]	"U" value [W/m ² K]	R _{solar} [%]
Flat Roof	1.84	15	0.25	15	0.16	80	0.15	58
Pitched Roof	2.19	30	0.25	30	0.16	77	0.16	77
External wall	1.28	40	0.29	40	0.19	80	0.18	71
Internal walls (non-conditioned areas)	1.28	-	0.29	-	0.19	-	0.18	-
Ground floor	1.96	-	0.29	-	0.22	-	0.22	-
External floor	1.33	-	0.30	-	0.15	-	0.15	-
Windows	4.95	-	1.50	-	1.50	-	1.50	-
External door	2.82	-	1.80	-	1.80	-	1.80	-

5. Discussion of the first results for the Italian case study buildings

This section shows the results of thermal-energy dynamic simulation of the two Italian case study buildings in the five considered scenarios. Simulations have been performed under both thermostatically-controlled and free-running conditions, so as to assess achievable energy saving and passive indoor conditions improvements through the ZERO-PLUS technologies. Moreover, a thermal comfort analysis in operating systems conditions has been carried out.

5.1. Energy needs

Figures 5 and 6 show the results of building year round dynamic simulation under thermostatically-controlled conditions for the building Typology A and B, respectively, and for the five buildings models, i.e. Reference_typical, Reference_regulation, Baseline, Baseline+, and Zero Plus_reduction+generation. The annual operational energy needs of the five different scenarios for heating, cooling (apart from the Reference_typical buildings that have no cooling system), and DHW are reported in the first column, "HVAC+DHW". Whereas, buildings total energy needs, i.e. heating, cooling, DHW, lighting, and appliances, are reported in the second column, "Total Energy". Moreover, Table 3 and 4 report the single energy consumption and energy production contributions for the first three and for the last two building scenarios, respectively. While, the energy consumption reduction results for each of the considered ZERO-PLUS technology implemented in the Zero Plus_reduction+generation scenario, as above mentioned, are shown in Table 5.

Figure 5. Different building scenarios annual energy needs [kWh/m²/y] (Typology A).

Figure 6. Different building scenarios annual energy needs [kWh/m²/y] (Typology B).

Table 3. Single energy needs for the first three buildings scenarios [kWh/m²/y].

Energy needs [kWh/m ² /y]	Reference_typical		Reference_regulation		Baseline	
	Typology A	Typology B	Typology A	Typology B	Typology A	Typology B
Heating	148.1	133.1	19.0	19.3	10.7	10.5
Cooling	-	-	2.1	1.7	0.9	0.7
DHW	4.0	3.6	1.2	1.1	0.7	0.7
Lighting	77.4	76.1	12.9	12.7	9.3	9.7
Appliances	15.5	15.0	15.4	14.7	15.4	15.0

Table 4. Single energy needs and energy production for the last two buildings scenarios [kWh/m²/y].

Energy needs [kWh/m ² /y]	Baseline+		Zero Plus_reduction+generation	
	Typology A	Typology B	Typology A	Typology B
Heating	7.9	7.8	7.5	7.5
Cooling	0.9	0.8	0.3	0.3
DHW	0.7	0.7	0.7	0.7
Lighting	9.3	9.7	9.3	9.7
Appliances	15.4	15.0	15.4	15.0
Generation by PV	-52.6	-52.6	-52.6	-52.6

Table 5. Results of each ZERO-PLUS reduction technology added separately to the building [kWh/m²/y].

	Energy consumption (HVAC+DHW) [kWh/m ² /y]	
	Typology A	Typology B
Baseline+	9.52	9.23
Baseline+ & FIBRAN XPS	9.51	9.21
Baseline+ & FIBRAN plaster	9.40	9.08
Baseline+ & FIBRAN tiles	9.45	9.19
Baseline+ & FREESCOO	8.87	8.70
Zero Plus_reduction+generation	8.60	8.42

The Baseline project buildings present much lower energy need compared to the Reference_typical buildings. Furthermore, the Baseline buildings are rather energy efficient if compared to the same buildings developed according to the current Italian building regulation, i.e. Reference_regulation. In fact, while the Reference_regulation buildings do not address the ZERO-PLUS target in terms of annual energy consumption, the Baseline buildings reach the goal of the project by consuming 12.4 kWh/m²/y < 20.0 kWh/m²/y for Typology A and 11.9 kWh/m²/y < 20.0 kWh/m²/y for Typology B. The further improvements to the buildings envelope and systems considered in the Baseline+ buildings allows a significant energy saving, in particular in terms of heating equal to 26 % for both building typologies. Finally, the Zero Plus_reduction+generation buildings reach the goal of the project by consuming 8.6 kWh/m²/y < 20.0 kWh/m²/y for Typology A and 8.4 kWh/m²/y < 20.0 kWh/m²/y for Typology B, i.e. 3.8 kWh/m²/y and 3.5 kWh/m²/y less than the Baseline buildings, respectively. Furthermore, each building in the Italian case study settlement produces 52.6 kWh/m²/y for both typologies, thanks to the building integrated PVs.

Considering the single ZERO-PLUS innovative technologies contribution, FIBRAN XPS and the standard XPS insulation of *DesignBuilder* present similar properties. Therefore, low differences in terms of thermal-energy performance are detected. FIBRAN plaster and FIBRAN tiles in the Zero Plus_reduction+generation buildings show lower values of solar reflectance if compared to the Baseline and Baseline+ buildings envelope components. Therefore, the Zero

Plus_reduction+generation buildings cooling consumption is slightly increased with respect to the other two scenarios, while the heating needs are reduced. Anyway, the total energy consumption is reduced, for both typologies of buildings, since the heating need reduction is higher than the cooling need increase, in the case study location climate conditions. Finally, *FREESCOO* HVAC system presents its best performance when operating for the reduction of cooling needs, due to its high electric efficiency in terms of EER. In fact, in the Zero Plus_reduction+generation buildings, cooling consumptions tend to be almost null. However, it has to be taken into account that *FREESCOO* uses thermal energy produced by the thermal energy producer system, such as a solar collector, in order to generate the required building cooling. Such energy consumption has not been considered in building simulation at this stage and will be considered in future steps of the work, when assessing the overall settlement energy balance.

5.2. Indoor environmental performance

Figures 7-10 report the results of buildings dynamic simulation under free-running conditions for winter and summer. The trends of indoor Operative Temperature in the five scenarios for the two building typologies are shown with respect to the Outdoor dry-bulb Temperature during the coldest week of winter (Figure 7 and 8), and the hottest week of summer (Figure 8 and 10).

The Zero Plus_reduction+generation buildings show the best performance in winter for keeping warmer and flatter along the day the indoor air temperature. Its performance is significantly increased with respect to the two Reference_typical and Reference_regulation buildings, with a maximum temperature difference equal to around 4 and 3 °C, respectively. In summer, the same Zero Plus_reduction+generation buildings are able to reduce the indoor thermal fluctuation and the daily hot peaks, therefore improving the indoor thermal comfort conditions. However, the most improved indoor comfort conditions are found for the Baseline and Baseline+ buildings, given the higher reflectance capability of their external facades and flat roof coatings.

Figure 7. Different building scenarios Indoor Operative Temperature trend during the coldest week of winter (Typology A).

Figure 8. Different building scenarios Indoor Operative Temperature trend during the coldest week of winter (Typology B).

Figure 9. Different building scenarios Indoor Operative Temperature trend during the hottest week of summer (Typology A).

Figure 10. Different building scenarios Indoor Operative Temperature trend during the hottest week of summer (Typology B).

5.3. Thermal comfort analysis

The results of thermal comfort analysis for the five scenarios of building Typology A and B are reported in the following Table 6, 7, 8, and 9 for winter, spring, summer, and autumn, respectively. Results show that almost all scenarios present good thermal comfort conditions (green values) in autumn, summer, and spring for both buildings typologies. The sole Reference_regulation buildings are slightly too hot in summer, while the Reference_typical scenario of both building typologies and the Baseline and Baseline+ scenarios of Typology B are too cold in spring. On the other hand, all buildings scenarios present too low temperatures in winter.

However, the thermal comfort is significantly improved in the Zero Plus_reduction+generation scenarios with respect to the corresponding Reference_typical and Reference_regulation. Accordingly, in all analyzed seasons and for both building typologies the thermal performance is progressively improved by moving from the Reference_typical scenario to the Zero Plus_reduction+generation. Furthermore, these results represent the average PMV and PPD values during the entire season, even during the time of the day when building zones were not occupied and, therefore, HVAC were not operating.

Table 6. Thermal comfort results under thermostatically-controlled conditions in winter.

Building scenarios	Operative Temperature [°C]	PMV [-]	PPD [%]
A_Reference_typical	15.10	-0.94	23.68
A_Reference_regulation	16.70	-0.66	14.27
A_Baseline	17.29	-0.56	11.51
A_Baseline+	17.31	-0.55	11.45
A_ZeroPlus_reduction+generation	17.36	-0.55	11.25
B_Reference_typical	14.77	-1.00	25.99
B_Reference_regulation	15.85	-0.81	18.73
B_Baseline	16.33	-0.72	15.99
B_Baseline+	16.33	-0.72	15.96
B_ZeroPlus_reduction+generation	16.39	-0.71	15.64

Table 7. Thermal comfort results under thermostatically-controlled conditions in spring.

Building scenarios	Operative Temperature [°C]	PMV [-]	PPD [%]
A_Reference_typical	18.78	-0.62	13.14
A_Reference_regulation	19.84	-0.41	8.51
A_Baseline	19.74	-0.42	8.74
A_Baseline+	19.73	-0.43	8.79
A_ZeroPlus_reduction+generation	19.89	-0.39	8.24
B_Reference_typical	18.51	-0.68	14.64
B_Reference_regulation	19.43	-0.49	9.97
B_Baseline	19.20	-0.52	10.74
B_Baseline+	19.21	-0.52	10.70
B_ZeroPlus_reduction+generation	19.37	-0.49	10.04

Table 8. Thermal comfort results under thermostatically-controlled conditions in summer.

Building scenarios	Operative Temperature [°C]	PMV [-]	PPD [%]
A_Reference_typical	24.78	0.41	8.55
A_Reference_regulation	25.20	0.51	10.53
A_Baseline	24.82	0.44	8.95
A_Baseline+	24.84	0.44	9.01
A_ZeroPlus_reduction+generation	25.05	0.49	9.98
B_Reference_typical	24.57	0.36	7.76
B_Reference_regulation	25.18	0.52	10.65
B_Baseline	24.62	0.40	8.37
B_Baseline+	24.68	0.42	8.61
B_ZeroPlus_reduction+generation	24.87	0.46	9.45

Table 9. Thermal comfort results under thermostatically-controlled conditions in autumn.

Building scenarios	Operative Temperature [°C]	PMV [-]	PPD [%]
A_Reference_typical	19.20	-0.45	9.30
A_Reference_regulation	20.42	-0.21	5.90
A_Baseline	20.70	-0.15	5.45
A_Baseline+	20.71	-0.15	5.44
A_ZeroPlus_reduction+generation	20.85	-0.12	5.28
B_Reference_typical	19.04	-0.49	9.92
B_Reference_regulation	20.21	-0.25	6.26
B_Baseline	20.40	-0.20	5.81
B_Baseline+	20.43	-0.19	5.77
B_ZeroPlus_reduction+generation	20.59	-0.16	5.54

6. Conclusions and future developments

The ZERO-PLUS project aims at bridging the gap between design at single building level and integrated settlement level. In fact, its main purpose is to develop a comprehensive and cost-effective system for Net Zero Energy settlements, composed of innovative solutions for the building envelope, for building energy generation and management, and for energy generation management at settlement level, to be rapidly spread on the market. In order to be optimally designed and developed, such system will be implemented and analyzed in four case study settlements in Europe, i.e. in Italy, Cyprus, France, and UK. The final target for these NZE settlements is to achieve less than

20 kWh/m²y of building energy need and more than 50 kWh/m²y of renewable energy production in each settlement, with at least 16% lower cost with respect to the current ones. The target will be achieved through the transition from single NZE buildings to NZE settlements, i.e. thanks to the integrated energy loads and resources management within the settlement. Moreover, an approach of mass customization will be employed so as to reduce balance of system costs.

In this framework, the present work described the general framework of the ZERO-PLUS project and reported the first design and assessment results for the Italian case study buildings. The four case study settlements layout and climatic context were briefly presented, together with the energy efficiency and renewable energy production technologies involved in the project. Moreover, the results of the thermal-energy performance analysis of the Italian case study buildings at preliminary design stage were shown. At this stage, the sole building integrated energy efficient systems and technologies for renewable energy production were taken into account, while technologies to be implemented at settlement level and energy management technologies will be considered in future project steps.

Findings of case study buildings simulation in terms of energy requirements showed that the Baseline project buildings present much lower energy need compared to both the Reference_typical and Reference_regulation buildings. The further implementation of EE strategies and the ZERO-PLUS innovative technologies, i.e. the FIBRAN advanced envelope components and the *FREESCOO* HVAC system, optimize the buildings energy performance. In fact, the Zero Plus_reduction+generation buildings reach the goal of the project by consuming 8.6 kWh/m²/y < 20.0 kWh/m²/y for Typology A and 8.4 kWh/m²/y < 20.0 kWh/m²/y for Typology B, i.e. 3.8 kWh/m²/y and 3.5 kWh/m²/y less than the Baseline buildings, respectively. Furthermore, each building in the Italian case study settlement produces 52.6 kWh/m²/y, thanks to the building integrated PVs. In terms of yearly thermal comfort analysis, the thermal performance is progressively improved by moving from the Reference_typical scenario to the Zero Plus_reduction+generation. In fact, both Zero Plus_reduction+generation building typologies present comfort indexes inside the tolerance range during the whole year, except for winter, when it is slightly too cold.

This work focused only on the thermal-energy analysis and integration of energy efficient technologies at building level. Future project steps will bridge the gap between building and community level by designing and integrating the single buildings in the settlement, in order to meet the project targets.

Acknowledgments

This work has received funding from the European Union Horizon 2020 Programme in the framework of the “ZERO-PLUS project: Achieving near Zero and Positive Energy Settlements in Europe using Advanced Energy Technology”, under grant agreement n° 678407. The authors thank the whole ZERO-PLUS partnership and the University of Athens group for cooperating in the work-in-progress success of the initiative and for the huge coordination effort. The first author acknowledgments are due to the “CIRIAF program for UNESCO” in the framework of the UNESCO Chair “Water Resources Management and Culture”, for supporting her research.

References

1. Santamouris, M. Innovating to zero the building sector in Europe: Minimising the energy consumption, eradication of the energy poverty and mitigating the local climate change. *Sol Energy*, In Press.
2. Fanney, A.H.; Payne, V.; Ullah, T.; Ng, L.; Boyd, M.; Omar, F.; Davis, M.; Skye, H.; Dougherty, B.; Polidoro, B.; Healy, W.; Kneifel, J.; Pettit, B. Net-zero and beyond! Design and performance of NIST's net-zero energy residential test facility. *Energy and Buildings* **2015**, *101*, 95–109.
3. Kapsalaki, M.; Leal, V.; Santamouris, M. A methodology for economic efficient design of Net Zero Energy Buildings. *Energy and Buildings* **2012**, *55*, 765–778.
4. Lopes, R.A.; Martins, J.; Aelenei, D.; Lima, C.P. A cooperative net zero energy community to improve load matching. *Renewable Energy* **2016**, *93*, 1–13.
5. Cellura, M.; Guarino, F.; Longo, S.; Mistretta, M. Energy life-cycle approach in Net zero energy buildings balance: Operation and embodied energy of an Italian case study. *Energy and Buildings* **2014**, *72*, 371–381.
6. Coppi, M.; Quintino, A.; Salata, F. Numerical study of a vertical channel heated from below to enhance natural ventilation in a residential building. *International Journal of Ventilation* **2013**, *12* (1), 41–49.
7. Kylili, A.; Fokaides, P. A. European smart cities: The role of zero energy buildings. *Sustainable Cities and Society* **2015**, *15*, 86–95.
8. European Parliament and Council of the European Union, EPBD - Energy Performance of Buildings Directive 2010/31/EU of 19 May 2010, Off. J. Eur. Union. Available online: <http://eur-lex.europa.eu/LexUriServ/LexUriServ.do?uri=OJ:L:2010:153:0013:0035:EN:PDF> (accessed on 9th March 2016).
9. *IEA SHC Task 40 / ECBCS Annex 52: Net Zero Energy Solar Buildings*, 2011. Available online: <http://task40.iea-shc.org/> (accessed on 9th March 2016).
10. Salata, F.; Golasi, I.; Vollaro, E.L.; Bisegna, F.; Nardecchia, F.; Coppi, M.; Gugliermetti, F.; Vollaro, A.L. Evaluation of different urban microclimate mitigation strategies through a PMV analysis. *Sustainability* **2015**, *7* (7), 9012–9030.
11. Salata, F.; Golasi, I.; de Lieto Vollaro, R.; de Lieto Vollaro, A. Outdoor thermal comfort in the Mediterranean area. A transversal study in Rome, Italy. *Building and Environment* **2016**, *96*, 46–61.
12. Sartori, I.; Napolitano, A.; Voss, K. Net zero energy buildings: A consistent definition framework. *Energy and Buildings* **2012**, *48*, 220–232.
13. Wang, L.; Gwilliam, J.; Jones, P. Case study of zero energy house design in UK. *Energy and Buildings* **2009**, *41* (11), 1215–1222.
14. Garde, F.; David, M.; Lenoir, A.; Ottenwelter, E. Towards net zero energy buildings in hot climates: Part 1, new tools and methods. *ASHRAE Transactions* **2011**, *117*, 450–457.
15. Lenoir, A.; Thellier, F.; Garde, F. Towards net zero energy buildings in hot climate, part 2: Experimental feedback. *ASHRAE Transactions* **2011**, *117*, 458–465.
16. Kolokotsa, D.; Rovas, D.; Kosmatopoulos, E.; Kalaitzakis, K. A roadmap towards intelligent net zero- and positive-energy buildings. *Solar Energy* **2011**, *85* (12), 3067–3084.

17. Mlecnik, E. Defining nearly zero-energy housing in Belgium and the Netherlands. *Energy Efficiency* **2012**, 5 (3), 411–431.
18. Hamdy, M.; Hasan, A.; Siren, K. A multi-stage optimization method for cost-optimal and nearly-zero-energy building solutions in line with the EPBD-recast 2010. *Energy and Buildings* **2013**, 56, 189–203.
19. Garde, F.; Lenoir, A.; Scognamiglio, A.; Aelenei, D.; Waldren, D.; Rostvik, H.N.; Ayoub, J.; Aelenei, L.; Donn, M.; Tardif, M.; Cory, S. Design of Net Zero Energy Buildings: Feedback from International Projects, The 6th International Conference on Applied Energy – ICAE2014. *Energy Procedia* **2014**, 61, 995–998.
20. Becchio, C.; Bottero, M.C.; Corgnati, S.P.; Ghiglione, C. nZEB design: challenging between energy and economic targets, 6th International Building Physics Conference, IBPC 2015. *Energy Procedia* **2015**, 78, 2070–2075.
21. Skarning, G.C.J.; Hviid, C.A.; Svendsen, S. A Roadmap for improving roof and façade windows in nearly zero-energy houses in Europe. *Energy and Buildings* **2016**, 116, 602–613.
22. Carlisle, N.; Geet, O. Van; Pless, S. Definition of a “ Zero Net Energy ” Community. *National Renewable Energy Laboratory*, 2009, 1–14.
23. Wheeler, S.M.; Segar, R.B. Zero Net Energy At A Community Scale: UC Davis West Village. In *Energy Efficiency*; Fereidoon P. Sioshansi, Eds.; Publisher: Academic Press Boston, Massachusetts, USA, 2013; pp. 305–324.
24. Chance, T. Towards sustainable residential communities; the Beddington Zero Energy Development (BedZED) and beyond. *Environment and Urbanization* **2009**, 21 (2), 527–544.
25. Heinze, M.; Voss, K. Goal: Zero Energy Building - Exemplary Experience Based on the Solar Estate *Solarsiedlung Freiburg am Schlierberg*, Germany. *Journal of Green Building* **2009**, 4 (4), 93–100.
26. HORIZON 2020, The EU Framework Programme for Research and Innovation. Available online: <https://ec.europa.eu/programmes/horizon2020/> (accessed on 9th March 2016).
27. Pisello, A.L.; Piselli, C.; Cotana, F. Thermal-physics and energy performance of an innovative green roof system: The Cool-Green Roof. *Solar Energy* **2015**, 116, 337–356.
28. Peel, M.C.; Finlayson, B.L.; McMahon, T.A. Updated world map of the Köppen–Geiger climate classification. *Hydrology and Earth System Sciences* **2007**, 11, 1633–1644.
29. FIBRAN Energy Shield. Available online: <http://www.fibran.com/> (accessed on 9th March 2016).
30. FREESCOO. Available online: <http://www.freescOO.com/> (accessed on 9th March 2016).
31. SBskin Smart Building skin. Available online: <http://www.sbskin.it/> (accessed on 9th March 2016).
32. WindRail, ANERDGY. Available online: <http://www.anerdgy.com/> (accessed on 9th March 2016).
33. ABB, Automation and Power technologies. Available online: <http://www.abb.com/> (accessed on 9th March 2016).
34. U.S. Department of Energy, Energy Efficiency and Renewable Energy. Building Technologies Program: EnergyPlus, 2014.
35. *IEE Project TABULA: Typology Approach for Building Stock Energy Assessment*, 2009-2012. Available online: <http://episcOpe.eu/iee-project/tabula/> (accessed on 9th March 2016).
36. Ministero dello Sviluppo Economico, Repubblica Italiana, Decreto interministeriale 26 giugno 2015 - Applicazione delle metodologie di calcolo delle prestazioni energetiche e definizione delle prescrizioni e dei requisiti minimi degli edifici. Available online:

<http://www.sviluppoeconomico.gov.it/index.php/it/normativa/decreti-interministeriali/2032966-decreto-interministeriale-26-giugno-2015-applicazione-delle-metodologie-di-calcolo-delle-prestazioni-energetiche-e-definizione-delle-prescrizioni-e-dei-requisiti-minimi-degli-edifici> (accessed on 9th March 2016).

37. EN ISO 7730. Ergonomics of the Thermal Environment – Analytical Determination and Interpretation of Thermal Comfort Using Calculation of the PMV and PPD Indices and Local Thermal Comfort Criteria, 2005.